

BULLYING IN AN INCLUSIVE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: The article reveals the theoretical problem of bullying in an inclusive environment. The specific conditions for the emergence of bullying and the development of bullying are given, as well as a number of preventive measures to prevent bullying.

Key words: bullying, inclusive environment, teenager, educational standard, bullying.

Introduction

The 2006 Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities states that “disability is the result of interactions that occur between persons with impairments and environmental barriers that prevent their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.” The convention also recognizes the diversity of people with disabilities, which “includes persons with long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments” [1].

Inclusion in educational settings is a key strategy for ensuring equal access to learning and social inclusion for all students, regardless of their individual characteristics. However, the introduction of inclusive education does not exclude problems associated with bullying. Bullying in inclusive environments can take specific forms and place special demands on prevention and intervention methods. D. Lane and E. Miller understand bullying as a long-term process of conscious cruel treatment, physical and (or) mental, on the part of one or a group of children towards another child (other children) [2].

In Uzbekistan, the introduction of an inclusive form of education into the educational standard inevitably leads to the emergence of a number of problems, and one of them is bullying.

For example, a national study of elementary and secondary school students in the United States found that students with disabilities were victims of bullying as often or one and a half times more often than students without disabilities [3].

According to a study in rural US schools, girls with disabilities were almost four times more likely to be bullied than their peers without disabilities, and boys with disabilities were two and a half times more likely than boys without disabilities [4].

According to the UNESCO World Education Monitoring Report, the countries of Central and Eastern Europe and the countries of the Caucasus and Central Asia are transitioning to inclusive education based on human rights.

- Over the past 20 years, the number of children out of school has been halved.
- In two out of every three educational systems, the definition of inclusion includes a wide variety of marginalized groups.
- Countries are using the medical model of inclusion much less. The percentage of children in special schools has fallen from 78% in the 2005/06 school year. up to 53% in 2015/16 The percentage of children in institutions fell by 30% over the same period.
- Schools are looking to expand their services and make them more flexible. Of the 30 educational systems analysed, 23 use counseling and mentoring, 22 use teaching assistants for children with learning difficulties, and 21 support specialists and speech therapists.

- But the transition to a policy of inclusion is far from complete.
- One in three students in Central and Eastern Europe is still in a special school.
- In Georgia, Kazakhstan and Mongolia, the proportion of children with disabilities not attending school is twice as high as the number of such children attending school.
- In 15 out of 30 educational systems, admission to school is determined by the conclusion of a medical-psychological commission and other selection procedures.
- What is considered inclusive pedagogy in some countries may in practice only be working with medically determined disabled people. In Belarus, integrated classes use two programs - a regular one for general education and a second one for special education, and joint education covers only a limited range of subjects [5].

Methodology and method

An inclusive educational environment strives to create conditions in which all students can participate in the learning process on equal terms. However, the unique aspects of inclusive education create specific conditions for the emergence and development of bullying:

1. Student diversity. Inclusive classes bring together children with different educational needs and abilities. This diversity can become a source of bias and prejudice, leading to more frequent bullying.
2. Need for additional support. Pupils with special educational needs often require additional support, which can cause envy or hostility from other pupils, contributing to bullying.
3. Interest and misunderstanding. Lack of awareness of the needs and characteristics of children with special needs can lead to misunderstandings and stereotypes, which in turn contribute to negative attitudes and bullying.

Bullying in an inclusive environment has serious consequences for everyone involved. For the victim of bullying, this can manifest itself in the form of stress, anxiety, depression and decreased academic performance, while for the bully it can become a habitual behavior that will manifest itself in other areas of life. Bystanders may also experience emotional distress and a sense of indifference to the cruelty. In an inclusive class, the risk of bullying can be determined by several factors: The presence of specific physical and psychological characteristics in children with disabilities [6].

To determine the participants in bullying (victim, buller, defender, observer), a methodology is used to identify the “Bullying structure” developed by E.G. Norkina, consisting of 25 questions, three of which allow us to find out about the presence of bullying in the classroom, both from the teacher, so does the student. This technique provides us with the opportunity to determine the “bullying structure” in the classroom [7].

Conclusions

To minimize bullying in an inclusive educational environment, comprehensive measures should be taken:

1. Educational programs. Conducting training programs for students, teachers and parents on the importance of inclusion, respect for diversity and methods of preventing bullying.
2. Create a supportive environment. Creating a culture of mutual respect and support within the educational institution, including the involvement of all members of the school community.
3. Monitoring and evaluation. Regularly monitor classroom behavior and conduct anonymous surveys to identify cases of bullying and evaluate the effectiveness of measures taken.
4. Professional training. Training teachers and school administrators in methods of early detection and intervention in cases of bullying, as well as working with children who have been bullied.

5. Support for victims. Ensuring the availability of psychological support and counseling for students who have been bullied in order to restore their psychological state and self-esteem

Thus, bullying in an inclusive educational environment is a complex problem that requires an integrated approach to solution. Understanding the specifics of bullying in the context of inclusion, as well as implementing effective prevention and intervention strategies, are key to creating a safe and supportive educational environment for all students.

Continuing research and developing practical recommendations on this topic will help improve the quality of inclusive education and reduce the level of bullying in educational institutions.

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